

Investigation of geometrical and composite material parameters for tension-absorbing bolted joints

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Motivation

- In the event of aircraft crash, the fuselage cross-section tends to ovalise
- Under such loadings, conventional joints are used to join the passenger and cargo floor cross-beams tend to fail in bolt fracture
- A novel joint named 'tension-absorbing joints' absorbs energy in tension and are designed to protect the bolt from early failure
- A simplified version of this joint is a pin pulling through a composite specimen
- The performance of these joints are evaluated by observing maximum bearing strength, mean crushing stress and specific energy absorption, for different geometrical and material parameters at quasi-static loading

Figure 1: Typical survivable crash scenario

Figure 2: Conventional joint behaviour under crash loading

Figure 3: Tension absorbing joint behaviour under crash loading

Materials and Methods

- HexPly® IM7/8552 carbon-epoxy was selected, as it is widely used in industry
- Two different specimen geometries and pin diameters (8 and 12 mm) were used to determine their effect on performance of these joints
- Laminate stacking sequence was varied to see the effect of ply grouping on mechanical performance of these joints
- A specialized experimental rig was designed to perform pin bearing tests, see Figure 4, at quasi-static rate

Figure 4: Force-displacement response for different layup specimen of thickness 2 mm, width 80 mm and tested with pin diameter 12 mm for plies grouping (a) blocked and (b) interspersed

Test Parameters

Figure 5: Geometries investigated and test setup

Layup No.	Stacking Sequence	
	Interspersed (IP)	Blocked (BK)
1	$[45/90/-45/0]_{2z}$	$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_z$
2	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2z}$	$[0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2]_z$
3	$[45/-45/90/0]_{2z}$	$[45_2/-45_2/90_2/0_2]_z$

Table 1: Stacking sequences

Results & Discussions

- For specimens having stacking sequence Layup 3 from Table 1, pin off-axis movement and spread of damage to the specimen edge were avoided
- Net-tension failure was occurred with narrow specimen due to small width-to-diameter ratio, for this reason a wider specimen geometry is selected for future studies
- Maximum bearing strength, mean crushing stress and specific energy absorption decreased with increasing pin diameter
- For each lay-up, blocking of plies resulted in lower strength, crushing stress and specific energy absorption

Figure 6: Effect of pin diameter on (a) maximum bearing stress, (b) mean crushing stress and (c) energy absorption for blocked ply layups

Figure 7: Effect of pin diameter on (a) maximum bearing stress, (b) mean crushing stress and (c) energy absorption for interspersed ply layups